

FACTSHEET #FS2.1-11

Greenhouse-integrated
atmospheric water
condensation for nursery
irrigation

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//01. QUICK FACTS

TECHNOLOGY TYPE

Passive atmospheric water condensation system integrated into greenhouse structures for supplementary nursery irrigation

INPUTS

Ambient air humidity

OUTPUTS

Highly pure condensate water for nursery irrigation

INDICATIVE MATURITY LEVEL

TRL 6

CONTEXT & SCALE

Greenhouse-based nursery production

KEY BENEFITS

Supplementary continuous water source; improved nursery irrigation water quality; provision of shading for rootstocks

MAIN CONSTRAINTS

Dependence on climatic conditions (night-time cooling and humidity); volume of recovered water limited in comparison to full irrigation demand; seasonal variability of condensate production

CATEGORY

Atmospheric water condensation

//02. WHAT IT IS

The greenhouse-integrated atmospheric water condensation system is a passive Nature-based Solution that recovers water from ambient air humidity under greenhouse conditions. It does that by condensing moisture on surfaces that cool below the dew point during clear nights. The collected condensate is stored for reuse in

nursery irrigation. It can also be used for improving irrigation water quality by blending with more saline primary water sources. The collected condensate is collected and stored for reuse in nursery irrigation. It can also be used for improving irrigation water quality by blending with more saline primary water sources.

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//03. WHY IT MATTERS

In Mediterranean greenhouse nursery systems, reliable water availability can be a limiting factor during long, dry summer periods with high evapotranspiration. Continuous irrigation is essential to maintain stable rootstock production under these conditions.

By passively recovering water from ambient air humidity, this condensation solution

provides a supplementary water source. The recovered condensate is of high purity and can be used directly for irrigation or to improve overall irrigation water quality, supporting more stable nursery operations under water-limited conditions. In addition, the passive use of existing structures reduces cost and makes adoption easier.

//04. DESIGN AND SIZING

The atmospheric water condensation system can be directly integrated into the greenhouse structure, which serves as the mounting framework for condensation units. The system consists of modular condensation panels installed externally along the greenhouse frame at elevated height. The panels are mounted at an inclination of approximately 30°, facilitating gravity-driven condensate drainage and optimising collection efficiency.

Each panel is composed of an insulating layer of 5cm XPS, covered with a thin, infrared-emissive carbon-black pigmented

PE foil that enhances nocturnal radiative cooling and enables water vapor condensation when surface temperatures fall below the dew point. Condensed water drains into collection gutters and is conveyed to a central storage unit for reuse. Generally, materials/coatings selection should balance cooling performance with food-safe runoff and durability.

Under suitable climatic conditions, the system can generate significant volumes of high-purity water (on the order of 20-120 liters per square meter and year).

Schematic illustration of a Greenhouse-integrated atmospheric water condensation for nursery irrigation © ANRI 2025

//05. HOW IT WORKS

The system passively condenses water vapour from the air by cooling the panel surfaces below the dew point through nocturnal infrared radiation of the highly IR radiative surface towards the clear sky. Under suitable microclimatic conditions (low wind, not too low dew point), moisture from the air condenses on the panel surfaces.

Once water vapour condenses on the panel's surfaces, it flows by gravity into integrated gutters and is collected in a central storage unit. The recovered condensate is of high purity and can be reused directly for greenhouse irrigation or blended with other water sources, supporting water management in nursery production systems.

//06. OPERATION, MAINTENANCE AND MONITORING

The system operates passively under suitable night-time conditions and is integrated into normal greenhouse operations. No active control or energy input is required.

Basic visual checks ensure panels, drainage and storage remain clean, correctly

positioned and unobstructed. The collected water is stored and reused within the greenhouse.

//07. RISKS & MITIGATION

The system's performance and output volume depends on suitable climatic conditions particularly clear nights with sufficient radiative cooling, a dew point not more than ~10°C below ambient temperature, and moderate wind conditions. As a

result, suitability of the greenhouse site should be checked and verified. Water contamination from materials or bird activity can compromise water quality. This can be mitigated via first-flush diversion and covered/closed storage.

//08. GOOD FIT FOR

Greenhouse nursery systems in warm and dry or semi-arid climates with frequent clear night skies where sufficient night-time cooling and ambient air humidity allow for passive condensation to occur. The solution is particularly suited to locations seeking low-energy, supplementary pure

water sources to support nursery irrigation under seasonal water scarcity.

Within the GEORGIA project, this solution is implemented in a [greenhouse nursery for citrus rootstock production at Phassouri Plantations in Limassol, Cyprus.](#)

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//09. KEYWORDS

Atmospheric condensation; Passive water harvesting; Greenhouse integration; Supplementary irrigation; Low-energy solution;

For more information visit: [GEORGIA EU Project](#)

//10. FURTHER READING RESOURCES

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